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PETROGRAPHY OF UPPER NARI FORMATION, GANDRI JABAL, PAKISTAN

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Abstract: The petrographic study has been well carried out in order to understand the mineralogical and geochemical characteristics of the Nari Formation at “Gandri Jabal” section near Nooriabad, Jamshoro. The formations were found to be mainly composed of sandstone, limestone, shale and variegated clays in the studied section. Sandstones are compact to semi-compact, ferruginous, fine to coarse grained and range from pinkish, reddish, brownish to camel in color. It was unusual that one bed of camel colored limestone with mega fossils was observed in the upper part of the formation. Petrographic study of the Gandri Jabal Section, Upper part of Nari Formation on the texture of most of the samples is medium to coarse grained as well as the shape of the grains is angular to sub-angular. Dominant cementing material is calcite along iron oxide. It was further justified by geochemical analysis of major elements through automated Scanning Electron Microscopy Energy Dispersive Spectrometer (SEM-EDS), that the highest peak was silicon (Si), the second dominant peak was of calcium (Ca), and a third dominant peak was fermium(Fe). This mean that the major mineral constituent was quartz and within the sandstone the cementing material is calcite and iron oxide, and highly calcium (Ca) bed found means that major mineral constituent was Calcite within mega fossils limestone. These finding demonstrate that majority of the lithologic units of this formation are daltatic or beach and one bed is in Marine environment as considered by earlier workers. The samples having higher proportion of quartz grains belonging to quartz arenite category. Hence it is concluded based on the shape of detrial quartz grains, that the source of these sediments neither came from northern Himalayan nor from Indian shield, but very likely came from the western highlands and on the basis of the present rock fragments, we conjecture that source is igneous, sedimentary or metamorphic.

Keywords: *Nari Formation, Petrographic Analyses, Kirthar Range, Quartz Arenite, Rock Fragments*

1. Introduction

The Nari series derived from the Nari river in the Khirthar Range (Blandford, 1876) and the Nari series of Blandford modified into Nari Formation (Williams, 1959) are exposed extensively in the Kirthar and Sulaiman region, whereas scattered outcrops are found in tectonic sedimentary thrust blocks in the Balochistan ophiolite-and-thrust belt. In the Kirthar Province, it conformably overlies the Kirthar Formation except in the Hyderabad anticlinorium where it oversteps and unconformably overlies the Kirthar and Laki Formations. The type section is in the Gaj River gorge in the Kirthar Range. The upper part of Nari Formation is mostly brown, fine- to coarse-grained sandstone (locally conglomeratic) with interbeds of shale. The lower part consists of interbedded gray to brown, fossiliferous sandy limestone, calcareous sandstone, and shale. At many, localities the lower part of the Formation is a grey to brown shelly, nodular, thick bedded to massive limestone which has been named the Nal Member (HSC 1960). The thickness of the Nari Formation ranges from 1,045 m to 1,820 m in the Kirthar area. It contains a rich fauna including echi~oids, molluscs, corals, foraminifera, and algae (Duncan et al. 1963, Khan 1968, Iqbal 1969b). Some of the significant larger foraminifera include *Nummulites intermedius*, *N. Vascus*, *N. Fichteli*, *N. Clipens*, and *Lepidocyclina di/atata*. The age of the Nari Formation is Oligocene to Early Miocene (Rupelian to Early Aquitanian; Latif 1964, Khan 1968).

The Nari Formation is exposed in different sections of the Laki and Khirthar Ranges but for the current investigation, the “Gadri Jabal Noriabad” is chosen due to easy access and proper exposure to this Formation. The Nari Formation of “Gandri Jabal Nooriabad” is generally composed Ferruginous Sandstone, variegated clay, semi compacted and compacted coarse to fine-grained sandstone, Soft Shale, and one bed of camel color limestone.

The basal beds of upper Nari formation is mostly with brown to greenish-gray shale and sandstone, limestone, which is thin-bedded hard, compact and massive. A thin-bedded medium-grained sandstone which is soft, friable and greenish-gray shales. The top beds of this formation is ferruginous sandstone which is deposited under fluvatile environment.

2. Study Area

2.1 LOCATION AND ACCESSIBILITY

The Gandri Jabal can easily be located from Karachi as well as Jamshoro along the Super Highway, It is located some 10 Kilometers away from Super Highway near Power Cement Factory passing through Village” Walidad Jokhio” towards South. It can also be seen on Hunting Survey Sheet No# 35-LP(Figure 1).

Figure1. Location of Study Area

2.2 STRATIGRAPHY OF SRUDY AREA

In the studied area three formations; from older to younger Tiyon Formation, Nari Formation, Gaj Formation (Table. 1).The Upper contact unconformable between Tiyon and Nari Formation with appear the celestite mineral deposits at Tiyon Formation (Figure 2) and lower contact is conformable contact between Nari Formation with Gaj Formation (Figure 3).

Table. 1. Stratigraphy of studied area

Age	Formation	Lithology
Early Miocene	Gaj formation	Shale, Sandstone and Limestone
Oligocene	Nari Formation	Sandstone, limestone and Shale
Eocene	Tiyon Formation	Limestone

Figure2. Unconformable Upper contact and celestite mineral deposits, study area.

Figure3. Conformable lower contact, study area.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

3.1 SECTION MEASUREMENT

The reconnaissance survey section having maximum lithologic units was selected for sampling and columnar section. Measurement of the geological section was carried out with the layers measured directly whereas applicable the layers were measured with Tape and Brunton compass method. During the measuring the section 16 samples were collected in the field. Total thickness of Nari formation at Gandri Jabal is 299.59 meters, (982.9 feet) (Figure 4) which is measured with the Tape and Brunton compass method.

Figure 4. Columnar section of Nari formation at Gandri Jabal

3.2 LABORATORY MEASUREMENTS

3.2.1 PETROGRAPHY

The rock samples were trimmed into rectangular blocks and one side polished so that a smooth, flat surface was obtained for adherence to glass specimen plates. After the sample were glued to the glass specimen plates, the sample block, were trimmed and polished again, until an even surface ($\approx 0.3\text{mm}$) was obtained allowing maximum light distribution through the specimen plates. The 07 thin section were prepared at Laboratory Center for Pure and Applied Geology (CPA) Geology University of Sindh, Jamshoro, for study we use Transmitted Light Microscope LEICA 2500p and camera for photography were used LEICA DFC 290.

3.2.2 SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPE

The selected sample for using Scanning Electronic Microscope to identification of type, shape, size and cement of constituent grains. Selected samples were analyzed under scanning electron microscope; point, line, and general analysis done through Energy Dispersive X-ray Analysis System (EDS) (JEOL Scanning Electronic Microscope) at Advance Research Lab CPA Geology University of Sindh, Jamshoro.

4. Results

4.1 PETROGRAPHY

The petrographic studies of the sandstone samples revealed that mostly the Gandri Jabal Section, Upper part of Nari Formation which is suggesting that the texture of most of the samples is medium to coarse grained as well as the shape of the grains is angular to sub-angular, occasionally sub-rounded and Rocks fragments, The detail of the samples is as follows.

GJNR # 02

Lithic Arenite, Coarse grained, angular to sub angular, moderately to well sorted Calcite and iron oxide cement is present (PM 2). Quartz is dominant 60% with 30% of rock fragments, (PM 3) traces amount zircon (PM 1) and 10% matrix.

<p>PM 3. Zircon grains, GJNR#02, (XPL)</p>	<p>PM 4. Fine grain quartz, calcite and iron oxide, GJNR#02, (XP)</p>

GJNR # 04

Quartz Arenite, Fine-grained, sub angular to sub-rounded, moderately sorted (PM 4). Calcite and iron oxide cement is present. Quartz is dominant 90% with 10% of matrix and traces amount of zircon grain (PM 5).

PM 5. Rocks fragment, GJNR#2, (XPL)

PM 6. Zircon grain, GJNR#04, (XPL)

GJNR # 10

Quartz Arenite, Fine-grained, sub rounded to sub-angular moderated to poor sorted (PM 6). Calcite and iron oxide cement is present. Quartz is dominant 91%, Rock Fragment 3-4%, 6-7% matrix and traces amount of zircon grain (PM 7,8).

PM 7. Subangular to sub-rounded fine-grained Quartz, GJNR#04, (XPL)

PM 8. Subangular to sub-rounded fine-grained Quartz, GJNR#10, (XPL)

GJNR # 11

Quartz Arenite, Fine-grained, sub angular to angular, moderated to well sorted (PM 9). Calcite and iron oxide cement is present. Quartz is dominant 80-85%, rock fragment 4-5% (PM 10), 10% matrix and traces amount of zircon grain.

A photomicrograph showing subangular to sub-rounded fine-medium grained Quartz and zircon in a thin section of GJNR#11 under cross-polarized light (XPL). The grains are dark and irregularly shaped, surrounded by a lighter matrix. A red scale bar in the bottom right corner indicates 0.05mm.	
PM 9. Zircon grain, GJNR#10, (XPL)	PM 10. Subangular to sub-rounded fine-medium grained Quartz and zircon

GJNR # 15b

Ferruginous Sandstone, fine grained, angular to sub angular moderately sorted. Iron oxide cement is present. Quartz is dominant 65-70%, 23% iron oxide and 7% matrix (PM 11).

A photomicrograph showing a rock fragment in a thin section of GJNR#11 under cross-polarized light (XPL). The fragment is dark and irregularly shaped, surrounded by a lighter matrix. A red scale bar in the bottom right corner indicates 0.05mm.	
PM 11. Subangular to angular fine-grained Quartz, GJNR#11, (XPL)	PM 12. Rock fragment, GJNR#11, (XPL)

GJNR # 16a

Lithic Arenite, fine to coarse grained, angular to sub rounded, poorly to moderately sorted Calcite and iron oxide cement is present (PM 12). Quartz is dominant 60-65%, rock fragment 20-25% (PM 13), and 10% matrix.

<p>PM 13. Angular to sub-angular grained Quartz, iron oxide cementing, GJNR#15b, (XPL), (PPL)</p>	<p>PM 14. Dissimilarity of quartz grain size and shape, GJNR#16a, (XPL)</p>
<p>PM 15. Rock fragment of limestone,</p>	

4.2 SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPE

A scanning electron microscope with chemical analytical capability using energy dispersive analysis (SEM/EDX) is useful in mineralogy as a source of morphological and compositional data on individual mineral grains. Through the SEM we can also differentiate between the cementing material and matrix present within sample. Shape, size, and contact between grains are very helpful in determination of depositional environments and the provenance of sediments.

Samples having quartz, calcite, iron oxide, ilmenite and trace amount zircon were analyzed using SEM (JEOL scanning electron microscope), the following analysis were undertaken:

I. General Analysis

II. Point Analysis

III Line Analysis

GJNR # 03

The general elemental analysis and line analysis indicates that silicon, oxygen along with iron are the dominant elements of this sample (Figure 5). Therefore, it is clear that quartz is the major mineral constituent followed by iron oxide (SM 2). On the basis of such chemistry it was seen that dominant mineral is quartz while the second dominant mineral is iron oxide in the form of cementing material. Iron oxide shows in the kidney shape. The kidney shape of Iron is present in the form of (Hematite) (SM 1) and clay mineral. There are two point were selected in this sample. Based on such chemistry it was see those points are quartz and iron oxide grains (SM 2). On the basis of EDS analysis, it clearly indicated this sample is Ferruginous fine-grained sandstone

Figure5

<p>SM 1. Kidney shape of iron oxide (hematite), GJNR#03,</p>	<p>SM 2. Quartz grains iron oxide, GJNR#03, (SEM)</p>

GJNR # 04

The general elemental analysis and line analysis indicates that silicon, oxygen along with calcium are the dominant elements of this sample. Various indications in the line scan spectrum is zirconium and titanium in traces number of elements in this sample (Figure 6). It was seen that dominant mineral is quartz while the second dominant mineral is calcite in the form of cementing material and accessories mineral is zircon and ilmenite minerals (SM 3). There were four points selected in this sample. Based on such chemistry it was seen that the first point is quartz, second is calcite, third is ilmenite, fourth is zircon grain (SM 3). SEM imaging and petrography of whole thin section was studied carefully in which no feldspar was observed. On Mineralogical basis this sample is matured. Textural features of this sample show that the quartz grains are usually moderately sorted. Shape of grains is sub-angular to sub-rounded.

Figure 6. General elemental and Line analysis of GJNR#04, (EDS)

<p>SM 3. Quartz, calcite, ilmenite and zircon grains</p>	<p>SM 4. calcite grains, GJNR#12a, (SEM)</p>

GJNR # 12a

The general elemental analysis and line analysis indicates that calcium and oxygen are the dominant elements of this sample (Figure 7). Therefore, it is clear that calcite is the major mineral (SM 4). On the bases of point analysis, it observed that all point is belongs to calcite (SM 4). On the bases of EDS analysis, it clearly indicated this sample is limestone.

Figure 7. General elemental and Line analysis of GJNR#12a, (EDS)

GJNR # 14

The general elemental analysis and line analysis indicates that silicon, oxygen along with calcium are the dominant elements of this sample. Therefore, it is clear that quartz is the major mineral constituent followed by calcite, clay and iron oxide and the thin calcite oxide coating over quartz grains were indicated. The line scan spectrum demonstrates that aluminum is present in trace amount element in this sample (Figure 8). It was seen that dominant mineral is quartz while the second dominant mineral is calcite in the form of cementing material (SM 5). There were two points selected in this sample. Based on such chemistry it was seen that those points are quartz and calcite grains (SM 5). SEM imaging was studied carefully. On Mineralogical basis this sample is matured. Textural features of this sample show that the quartz grains are usually moderately sorted. Shape of grains is Sub Angular to Angular. On the bases of EDS analysis, it is quite obvious that this sample is Fine to Medium Grained Massive Sandstone.

Figure 8. General elemental and Line analysis of GJNR#14, (EDS)

SM 5. Quartz grains coating with Calcite, GJNR#14, (SEM)

5. Discussion

The present research project was to investigate the petrography of Upper Nari Formation at Gandri Jabal section. This project was selected to investigate mineral constituents and major element geochemistry of main lithologic units/lithofacies of this formation. The present investigation is to find the provenance and depositional environments of this formation. This formation is also being focused by several companies for the exploration of oil and gas. So many oil and gas-related companies are operative in the offshore, and their focus is the Nari Formation (Syed and Sheikh, 2009). Further, no geochemical analysis has been carried out from any aspect of the Nari Formation. The present study is an attempt to delineate some geological history of this formation, especially the source of sediments.

The thin section preparation and microscopy were accessible techniques for most geologists. However, the light mineral analysis still has strong advantages compared to chemical and other methods, because analyzing the complete framework of sandstone allows for the differentiation of textures of individual grains even if they are same on chemical and mineralogical basis.

Throughout the fieldwork, it was observed that the major lithologic units of formation are compact and semi-compact, ferruginous, fine to coarse-grained sandstones. In color, they range from reddish, pinkish, brownish to camel color. It was very interesting that a massive and compact bed of camel color limestone with mega fossils is exposed before the ferruginous sandstone in the upper part, which is used as a marker bed to distinguish between the Nari and Gaj formation. However, differential weathering at different places is also a common phenomenon of this formation at this particular place. During fieldwork, it was noticed that the lower contact of Nari Formation with Tiyon formation is unconformable. Near this contact shows the loose sand and celestite mineral in the form of the honeycomb structure is the common phenomenon (Figure 2). During the fieldwork; it was observed that the basal part, which is composed of limestone, was not fully exposed and so far the upper part of the Nari Formation was selected for the present study. The presence of limestone deposits, cycles of clastic rocks, the reappearance of limestone and finally the ferruginous sandstones points towards transgression and regression in sea level. Also, the presence of limestone in the basal and again in the upper part along with different erosional features within clastic rocks indicates that sea-level fluctuation was dominant during the Oligocene epoch. Moreover, the sediments of the same units within the Central part are mature both textural and mineralogical wise and point towards the beach or marginal deltaic deposits.

Table 2:

S. No.	Sample No.	Petrographical Observation		
		Shape	Sorting	Mineral Composition (visual estimate)
01	GJNR-02	Angular to sub-angular	Moderately to well sorted	Quartz 60%, Rock Fragments 30%
02	GJNR-04	Sub-angular to sub-rounded	Moderately sorted	Quartz 90%
03	GJNR-10	Sub-rounded to sub-angular	Moderated to poor sorted	Quartz 91%, Rock Fragments (3-4%)

04	GJNR-11	Sub-angular to angular	Moderated to well sorted	Quartz (80-85%), Rock Fragments (4-5%)
05	GJNR-15b	Angular to sub-angular	Moderately sorted	Quartz (65-70%)
06	GJNR-16a	Angular to sub-angular	Poorly to Moderated sorted	Quartz (60-65%), Rock Fragments (20-25%)

The selected samples from major rock units/lithofacies were investigated based on different petrographic analyses (Table 2). The applied techniques such as the petrography and SEM-EDS analyses indicate that the dominant mineral of the studied sandstones is quartz, which is generally above 60% and some units reached up to 94%. The second dominant mineral is calcite while iron oxide is also present in a significant amount trace amount of zircon is also there, especially within the central portion of the upper part. Though earlier studies (Farshori, 1972, Shah 1997, Shah 2009) show that the basal part of Nari Formation is marine in origin, whereas the central and upper part is generally fluvial but present petrographic and field studies indicate that these units (i.e., central and upper) are not completely fluvial in origin. Based on the present study, it has been seen that some units of the upper part belong to the transitional environment possibly the beach deposits (e.g., sample # GJNR-10). Fine to medium-grained, moderately sorted quartz is the dominant constituent along with traces of zircon. After the deposition of sample # GJNR-10, the presence of camel-colored limestone (sample # GJNR-12) is a clear indication of the marine environment and needs more attention for micro-paleontological studies to constrain more geological history of the Nari Formation particularly in the Lower Indus Basin.

6. Conclusion

The study shows that the source possibly of this section is from north western parts of the study area. Most of samples were found to be composed of Ferruginous Sandstone, soft variegated clays, fine to coarse grained, compacted to semi compacted Sandstones and one unit of camel color limestone. The Gandri Jabal Section, Upper part of Nari Formation was deposited in daltatic or beach and one bed is in Marine environment. Through our petrographic investigations of the Gandri Jabal Section, Upper part of Nari Formation we concluded that the texture of most of the samples is medium to coarse grained as well as the shape of the grains is angular to sub-angular,

occasionally sub-rounded. So it means that the sediments have not traveled a lot of distance and their source may not be far away.

References

- Blanford, W. T., (1876). On the geology of Sind. *Ibid.*, Rees., Vol. 9, 8-22.
- Blanford, W. T., (1879). The geology of western Sind. *Ibid.*, Mem., Vol. 17, 1 -196.
- Noetling Fritz., (1905) Vorlaufige miltalung Uber die Gliedering de terlian Formation in Westlichen (Sindh, India) Centrall. Fur Mineral. Geol: paleont: V. (6),129-137 and 161-172.
- Williams, M. D., (1959). Stratigraphy of the Lower Indus Basin, West Pakistan. World Petroleum Cong., 5th New Your, Proc., Sec, I, 19, 377-390.
- Hunting Survey Corporation (1961). Reconnaissance geology of part of west Pakistan (Colombo plan cooperative project); Canada Govt. Toronto. 550.
- Folk, R.L., 1968, *Petrology of Sedimentary Rocks*: Hemphill's Publishers, Austin,Texas, USA, 170 p.
- Iqbal, M.W.A., 1969, *Mega-fauna from the Ghazij Formation (lower Eocene), Quetta-Sharig Area, West.*
- Farshori, M.Z., 1972, *The Geology of Sind*: Department of Geology, University of Sind, Jamshoro, Sind, Pakistan, 81 p.
- Iqbal, M.W.A., and S.M.I. Shah, 1980, *A guide to the stratigraphy of Pakistan: Geological Survey of Pakistan, Quetta, Pakistan, v. 53, 37 p.*
- Iqbal, M.W.A., and S.M.I. Shah, 1980, *A guide to the stratigraphy of Pakistan: Geological Survey of Pakistan, Quetta, Pakistan, v. 53, 37 p.*
- Yeats, R,S.,and Lawrence, R.D., 1984. Tectonics of the Himalayan thrust belt in northern Pakistan, in Haq, B.U., and Milliman, J.D., eds., *Marine Geology and Oceanography of Arabian Sea and coastal Pakistan*: New York, Van Nostrand Reinhold, p. 177-198.
- Usmani, P., Ahmed, M.R. (1986.b). Paleocology of Palaeoene Benthonic smaller foraminifera form the Lakhra area, Sindh, Pakistan: *NeuesJahrbuch fur Geology and paleoMonatshefte*, No.9, p. 570-576.
- Tucker, M., (1991). *Sedimentary Petrology. An introduction to the origin of sedimentary rocks*, Blackwell's Scientific, Oxford, Ed. 2nd, 260Pp.

- Solangi, H., Sarfaraz, (1992). Geophysical / Sedimentological studies of a Quaternary tidal delta system, Ph. D. thesis, University of Wales, U.K., 90.
- Kadri, I.B., 1995, Petroleum Geology of Pakistan: Pakistan Petroleum Limited, Karachi, Pakistan, 275 p.
- Kazmi, A., 1997, Geology and Tectonics of Pakistan: Graphic Publishers, Karachi, Pakistan, 554 p.
- Laghari, A., 2005, Petrology of the Nagarparkar granite and associated basic rocks, Thar Desert, Sindh, Pakistan: Ph. D. Thesis, National Center of Excellence in Geology, University of Peshawar, Peshawar, Pakistan, 297 p.
- Quraishi, I.H., S.A.A. Shah, M.A. Tariq, M.S. Khan, S.N. Ahsan, and M.L. Khanzada, 2001, Geological map of Karachi area, Sindh Pakistan: Geological Survey of Pakistan, : Graphic Publishers.
- I. SIDDIQUI, A.D. Memon, (2005): Petroleum geology Hydrocarbon Prospect of Sindh, Pakistan.
- K.M. Bangar , Revised & Enlarged Edition (2005),Principles Of Engineering Geology .
- Pakistan. Geol. Surv. Pakistan, Mem., Vol. 5, 27 p.
- Revista Mexicana de Ciencias Geológicas, v. 25, núm. 2, 2008,p.247-260.
- Francisco Borrero • Frances Scelsi Hess • Juno Hsu Gerhard Kunze • Stephen A. Leslie • Stephen Letro Michael Manga • Len Sharp • Theodore Snow • Dinah Zike. (2008): Earth Science. Printed in the United States of America.
- Syed and Sheikh (2009) . Reservoir Potential of Lower Nari Sandstones in Indus Offshore.
- Shah., S.M.I.,(2009). Stratigraphy of Pakistan. Published by the Geological Survey of Pakistan. Vol.12, Islamabad, Pakistan
- Brohi, I.A., Bablani, S.A., Solangi, S.H., (2009),Geology and Economic significance of Tertiary rocks, Khorwari section, Surjan Anticline, ThanoBula Khan, Sindh, Sindh Univ. Res. Jour. (Sci.Ser.) Vol. 141 (1) p. 195-106.
- S. Boggs, Jr. 2009: second edition.,PETROLOGY OF SEDIMENTARY ROCKS., Published in the United States of America by Cambridge University Press, New York.

- Agheem, M. H., Solangi, S.H., Hakro, A. A. D., Mastio, A. S., and Siddique, I., (2011) Major element geochemistry of Basalts at Ranikot area, Lower Indus Basin, Pakistan, Publ. Jour. of Himal. Earth Sci. (44): (2) (2011) 33-43.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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